

AC Drive Side Ground Fault Location for DC/AC Systems Based on AC Phases and Grounding Resistor Voltages

José M. Guerrero, Gustavo Navarro, Kumar Mahtani, and Carlos A. Platero

Abstract—Power converters are essential for process optimization and electric drives control. However, the presence of both dc and ac currents in the same circuit makes the diagnosis and protection of this type of systems difficult. For this reason, a new ground fault location method for the controlled ac drive side of a dc–ac system is presented in this article. It is based on a grounding resistor placed at the midpoint of the dc bus, where its voltage is measured simultaneously with the ac drive side phase-neutral voltages. Applying a phasor operated equation, the faulty phase can be detected by angle comparison. Furthermore, an estimation of the fault location can be obtained. To verify the method, numerous simulations have been performed. The results show certain inaccuracies when the fault is close to the neutral of the system, which is inconvenient since the phasor equation requires precise values. In contrast, the ground arc resistance is not needed in the fault location process. The effectiveness of the method has been also corroborated through experimental tests on a 140 kW power converter, making the ground fault diagnosis in dc–ac systems practical and useful.

Index Terms—DC–AC power converters, electrical fault detection, fault currents, fault diagnosis, fault location, monitoring, power system faults.

I. INTRODUCTION

NOWADAYS, power converters are the main electric device used in electrical control and process optimization. Fed by the grid with a dc bus between two ac stages [1], [2] (see Fig. 1),

Fig. 1. Variable speed drive fed from the ac grid side.

i.e., grid and controlled ac drive side, a power converter can maintain certain operating conditions on the ac drive side thanks to the switching of isolated gate bipolar transistors (IGBTs) or other switching elements connected at the terminals of this dc bus [3], [4].

In order to consume energy from the grid or to feed the grid optimally, a sinusoidal waveform is rectified or a dc voltage is modulated into ac pulsed voltage with switching elements, respectively [5].

However, in case of a fault, systems with a high presence of power electronics are difficult to protect due to the transitions between ac and dc currents. In this situation, conventional protections could be inaccurate or several specific protections would be needed such as in IGBTs [6], in the ac grid side [7], in the dc bus [8], or in the ac drive side [9].

Ground faults are the most common faults in electrical devices. They occur between a hot conductor and ground or another external point of the circuit. The majority of them are caused by insulation degradation. In case of a double ground fault, leakage currents, phase overvoltage and system unbalancing appear, causing the faulty device to malfunction. To avoid it, numerous researches on ground fault diagnosis were done in photovoltaic plants [10], microgrids and distribution lines [11], [12], adjustable speed drives [13], controlled wind turbines [14] or synchronous generator rotors [15], and among others.

Once a ground fault appears, high arc resistances (or ground fault resistances) can cause inaccuracy on most of the protection and diagnostic devices used nowadays. What is more, the use of power converters adds more error to the ground fault location estimation due to the high-frequency signals that they bring on.

For this reason, in this article, a new method to locate ac ground faults on the controlled ac drive side of a dc–ac system is proposed. This idea was previously presented in a conference [1]. The method is based on the voltage measurement at the

José M. Guerrero is with the Energy and Fuels Department, ETSIME, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, 28003 Madrid, Spain (e-mail: josemanuel.guerrero@upm.es).

Gustavo Navarro is with the Spanish Public Research Centre on Energy, Environment and Technology, CIEMAT, Ministerio de Innovación, Ciencia y Universidades, 28037 Madrid, Spain (e-mail: gustavo.navarro@ciemat.es).

Kumar Mahtani and Carlos A. Platero are with the Automatic, Electric and Electronic and Industrial Computer Engineering Department, ET-SII, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, 28006 Madrid, Spain (e-mail: kumar.mahtani@upm.es; carlosantonio.platero@upm.es).

terminals of a grounding resistor placed between the midpoint of the power converter dc bus and ground. By comparing this voltage with the three phase-neutral voltages on the controlled ac drive side, the method can detect the fault and distinguish in which phase the fault takes place. This technique can be used as add-on to other detection devices such as the one proposed in [16].

This article is structured as follows. Section II presents a brief overview of the existing ground fault location and protection techniques for ac and dc systems. Section III details the theoretical principles of the proposed method. Section IV describes the simulation model and analyzes the computer simulations. Section V shows and discusses the results obtained in the experimental tests carried out on a 140 kW power converter. Finally, Section VI concludes this article pointing out the main discussion and contributions.

II. STATE OF THE ART

The protection of electric systems against ground faults is needed to prevent damages resulting from single phase short-circuits. The first indicator of a ground fault is the emergence of larger currents due to the leakage current [17]. In a first stage, the ground fault resistance R_f usually has a high value because the insulation is not so deteriorated. If the fault persists, the insulation deterioration reduces the fault resistance value, which makes the leakage current to increase. Finally, a zero-impedance short-circuit can occur.

Nowadays, detection and location of ground faults in power systems is a highly active research field. In this section, some of the most common methods are discussed.

A. AC Ground Fault Diagnosis

For ac ground fault detection and location, different methods are used attending to the electrical system protected.

In transmission lines, impedance or distance relays can be used to achieve good results [18]. They are based on the line's currents and voltages measurements and the subsequent calculation of the impedance. Characterizing the line in healthy conditions, the protection settings are defined. The relay is set to trip if the impedance seen in real-time is lower than a certain threshold. Depending on how low the measured impedance is with respect to the impedance in healthy conditions, the fault is located on the impedance diagram [19], but its accuracy can be reduced due to the fault resistance R_f .

Furthermore, in high voltage transmission and distribution lines, some methods based on traveling waves measurements are starting to be used in ground fault location [20]. If a fault occurs, the transitory provokes an overvoltage disturbance as a high-frequency wave that propagates through the line is added to a reflection wave when it arrives to the end [21]. Studying the wave travel between the ends, the ground fault can be located. Other methods try to improve the distance protection relays when they are installed in ac/dc systems. They are based on energy equations, which depend on the system parameters, phase and ground current and voltage measurements, fault location,

and fault resistance. The use of this equation allows the fault location and avoids distance relay malfunctions [22].

In the field of electrical machines, specifically in induction machines, there are many new diagnosis methods such as current waveforms transient analysis [23], continuous monitoring of the insulation health [24], or stray flux measurement, which can detect wiring failures or ground faults by evaluating the flux waveform with the use of sensors placed outside the machine [25].

As an example of diagnosis and protection of synchronous machines, a 100% stator to ground protection is presented in [26]. This protection is built with an adaptive undervoltage third harmonic protection relay (ANSI 27NTH) connected between the neutral of the synchronous machine and ground. Finally, another technique is focused on ac voltage injection in the neutral of the synchronous generator and phase voltage measurement to locate ground faults in real [27].

B. DC Ground Fault Diagnosis

Not only ac systems need diagnosis and protection against ground faults. In the case of dc systems, diagnosis methods and protection systems are also applied.

As in ac systems, traveling waves can be used in HVdc systems. In dc systems, the disturbance provokes a transitory disturbance in the constant value of the voltage waveform. With the same methodology as in ac systems, i.e., measuring the instant values of the overvoltage wave at adjacent nodes, the fault can be detected [28].

For dc grids, probe power units between the conductor and ground are used to locate ground faults [29]. With the line and the probes parameters, and the probe power unit current resonance frequency, the fault distance to the probe can be located.

There are other more complex techniques for diagnosis in dc systems, e.g., the method exposed in [30], which detects faults on the dc side of power converters by analyzing the charging and discharging rates of the capacitors placed on the dc bus.

Also, there are a number of generic techniques to detect faults and trip the protections on power converters, e.g., differential relays [31]. However, these techniques do not locate faults in the different sides of a power converter. Some differential systems could be used in the dc ground fault location [32].

In this article, a new specific controlled ac drive side ground fault location method is presented. It is based on the voltage measurement in a grounding resistor installed between the middle point of the dc bus and ground and on the phase-to-neutral voltages measurement on the ac drive side of the inverter that was already used to detect ground faults in [16].

III. DESCRIPTION OF THE NEW METHOD

The location method described in the following can be considered as an add-on for a detection device, which has been previously described in [16] and patented in [33].

In the preceding ground faults detection device, a grounding resistor R_{gnd} was connected between the midpoint of the dc bus and ground, which limits the fault current in case of a ground fault. R_{gnd} works similar to high resistance IT grounding

Fig. 2. Variable speed drive setup. From left to right: grounding resistor R_{gnd} at the midpoint of the battery pack, a voltage measurement U_{gnd} at its terminals, battery pack; three-phase power converter; load phase impedances, Z_a, Z_b, Z_c , and phase-neutral voltages are measured, U_{an}, U_{bn}, U_{cn} .

methods in ac systems. It also allowed to detect when a ground fault occurred on the dc side of the converter by measuring a voltage waveform with only the dc component, and afterward, its polarity was used to determine the faulty pole. Also, it could detect ac drive side faults. When an ac drive side fault occurred, an ac voltage waveform appeared between the terminals of the grounding resistor. The value of R_{gnd} should be chosen to also fulfill the different electrical safety standards.

The proposed location method enhances the mentioned ac detection procedure, locating the fault, identifying the faulty phase, and the percentage of the impedance of the ac side regardless of the ground arc resistance R_f . The method requires the load impedance value to be known, while the phase voltages and the grounding resistor voltage U_{gnd} have to be monitored.

In order to have a better comprehension of the method, the proposed system is displayed in Fig. 2. This figure shows a dc/ac system, then the dc bus provides the electric energy from a dc source instead from an ac grid side (compare Fig. 2 with Fig. 1). This configuration is commonly implemented in EV, where batteries are used to feed the drive. Also, in the ac drive side, a three-phase equivalent impedance is depicted emulating the parameters and load of the electric machine. The load impedances Z_a, Z_b , and Z_c are previously characterized, and then, connected to the ac side. Finally, a grounding resistor R_{gnd} is placed at the midpoint of the battery pack.

The impedances are supposed constant as the ground fault location method is carried out during a steady-state operation. Additionally, R_{gnd} has a high value to limit the value of the ground fault current.

Initially, in healthy conditions, the residual current, I_{res} , though the grounding resistor is zero, as expressed in the following equation:

$$I_{res} = I_a + I_b + I_c = 0. \quad (1)$$

After a time of operation t_0 a fault occurs on phase “c,” provoking a ground leakage current. Fig. 3 shows a ground fault throughout phase “c,” therefore, its impedance Z_c , is divided into two different parts (upstream and downstream with respect

Fig. 3. Faulty system. A fault occurs on phase “c,” being the impedance Z_c divided into two parts [upstream $(1-k) \cdot Z_c$ and downstream $k \cdot Z_c$].

to the fault). This way a new factor is defined k , which is the proportion of the impedance associated to the point in which the fault is taking place.

The faulty system is now defined by the following equations:

$$I_{res} = I_a + I_b + I_c \neq 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} U_{an} \\ U_{bn} \\ U'_{cn} \\ U''_{cn} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} Z_a & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & Z_b & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1-k)Z_c \\ -kZ_c & -kZ_c & 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} I_a \\ I_b \\ I_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$U_{cn} = U'_{cn} + U''_{cn} \quad (4)$$

$$U_{gnd} = -R_{gnd} \cdot I_{res} \quad (5)$$

where U_{cn}' and U_{cn}'' are the portions of U_{cn} upstream and downstream regarding to the ground fault as shown in Fig. 3.

The value of k can be estimated developing the expression (4) into (6)–(8)

$$U_{cn} = (1-k) Z_c \cdot I_c - kZ_c \cdot \left(\frac{I_a}{Z_a} + \frac{I_b}{Z_b} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$U_{cn} = (1-k) Z_c \cdot I_{res} - Z_c \cdot \left(\frac{I_a}{Z_a} + \frac{I_b}{Z_b} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$U_{cn} = -(1-k) Z_c \cdot \frac{U_{gnd}}{R_{gnd}} - Z_c \cdot \left(\frac{U_{an}}{Z_a} + \frac{U_{bn}}{Z_b} \right). \quad (8)$$

TABLE I
SIMULATION MODEL COMPONENTS

Component	Characteristic	Magnitude
Grounding resistor	R_{gnd}	4700 Ω
Battery	U_{DC}	490 V
Cable impedance	R_{wire}	1 Ω
	L_{wire}	60 μ H
Inverter	C	1.638 mF
AC inductive filter	L_{filter}	3 mH
Inductive load	R	12.5 Ω
(quarter part)	L	5 μ H

Fig. 4. Voltage phasor diagram for a ground fault in a certain position of the phase “c” with $R_f = 0 \Omega$.

And obtaining the final expression (9) for the value of k , as follows:

$$k = 1 + \frac{R_{gnd}}{U_{gnd}} \cdot \left(\frac{U_{an}}{Z_a} + \frac{U_{bn}}{Z_b} + \frac{U_{cn}}{Z_c} \right). \quad (9)$$

Beforehand, some theoretical conclusions can be drawn from (9).

First, as (9) is a phasor equation, a transformation from time domain to frequency domain shall be done by applying sine and cosine filters for the first harmonic as shown in the following:

$$a_{1i} = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{2}{N} \cdot u_i(t_k) \cdot \sin\left(\frac{2 \cdot \pi \cdot k}{N}\right) \quad (10)$$

$$b_{1i} = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{2}{N} \cdot u_i(t_k) \cdot \cos\left(\frac{2 \cdot \pi \cdot k}{N}\right) \quad (11)$$

$$U_i = \sqrt{a_{1i}^2 + b_{1i}^2} \cdot e^{-\text{atan}\left(\frac{a_{1i}}{b_{1i}}\right)}. \quad (12)$$

Second, the healthy state of the system makes the equation indeterminate. The addition of the three phase-to-neutral voltages are zero, but also U_{gnd} , as there is not fault current flowing through R_{gnd} .

Once a ground fault occurs, e.g., in phase “c” (see Fig. 3), an overvoltage on the faulty phase will cause an unbalance that makes the addition of the phase voltages different from zero. Also, U_{gnd} is different from zero because a fault current is circulating between the faulty point and R_{gnd} . Then, the indeterminacy is solved in case of fault.

Seeing that k must be a real number between 0 and 1, as it is a percentage of the faulty impedance, the two terms multiplied in (9) must be in counter-phase. In Fig. 4, a voltage phasor diagram is plotted to explain the idea. The point M is the neutral of the impedance that is at the same potential as the midpoint of the dc bus by symmetry. If a ground fault appears (point F in Fig. 4) in a certain part of a phase (in Fig. 4 the faulty one is the phase “c”), the phase-neutral voltage has near the same value but is divided in upstream and downstream the fault components U_{cn}'

and U_{cn}'' , which could also be seen in Fig. 3. Furthermore, a voltage difference between the midpoint M , and the faulty point F , U_{gnd} , appears in R_{gnd} . This voltage U_{gnd} has opposite polarity to U_{cn} . In case of faults with R_f , the tendency is the same, as the voltage drop between F and M is divided into $U_f + U_{gnd}$, but both have the same direction as the fault is merely resistive.

Finally, another observation contemplates the high arc resistance R_f ground faults in terms of sensitivity in the formula. The grounding term of (9) will have a large value due to the low voltage measured, where the addition of phases term will have a small value due to the slight unbalance between phases.

It must be remarked that for variable speed drives Z_a , Z_b , and Z_c depend on the motor’s type and operation condition (load/speed). Then, the phase equivalent impedances should be simultaneously calculated by the use of the output currents and voltages of the power converter. The recording time of the waves for the calculation of the impedances is small, some tens of milliseconds. During this time, it can be assumed that the speed of the motor is constant, so it can be considered as steady-state conditions.

IV. COMPUTER SIMULATIONS

In order to test the method, numerous simulations have been carried out. The simulations are based on MATLAB Simulink by modeling a three-phase variable speed drive in steady state and fed by dc voltage sources as shown in Fig. 5.

Then, the power converter provides ac current to an RL load of $50 + j\omega \cdot 2 \times 10^{-5} \Omega$. The parameters of the whole system are displayed in Table I.

The value of R_{gnd} has been set at 4.7 k Ω , to limit the fault current up to 51 mA, but other values could be used. Then, a healthy state simulation and some faulty simulations at 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% of phase “c” (see Fig. 5) on the ac drive side have been carried out for ground fault resistances with values 0 Ω , 2.3 k Ω , 4.7 k Ω , and 10 k Ω . The values of R_f have been selected because they are standard values for resistances and they correspond approximately to direct ground fault, 50%, 100%, and 200% of the grounding resistor value R_{gnd} placed at the midpoint of the dc bus, respectively, which allow the study of the fault resistance effect in the fault location process.

These fault resistances could model insulation degradation or arc-fault effects, as they can be modeled as resistors attending to the different arc current and lengths as it is analyzed in [34]. However, more research should be done in this field since the

Fig. 5. Simulink setup. From left to right: a $4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$ grounding resistor with its terminal voltage measurement; a battery pack with accessible midpoint; cable impedance; a capacitor; a three-phase power converter; filters; parasitic capacitances and phase-to-ground capacitances; a ground fault arc resistance; and a three-phase RL load with their phase voltage measurements.

Fig. 6. U_{an} and U_{gnd} voltage waveforms for healthy operation.

Fig. 8. U_{cn} and U_{gnd} voltage waveform for a simulation for a ground fault with arc resistance of $R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$ located at 25% of the phase impedance.

Fig. 7. U_{cn} and U_{gnd} voltage waveforms for a simulation for a ground fault with arc resistance of $R_f = 2.3 \text{ k}\Omega$ located at 25% of the phase impedance.

Fig. 9. U_{cn} and U_{gnd} voltage waveform for a simulation for a ground fault with arc resistance of $R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$ located at the 75% of impedance.

faults damage is related to this parameter, as the fault resistance is inversely proportional to the fault severity.

In Fig. 6, a 40 ms healthy operation simulation is shown. In the figure, U_{gnd} has neither ac nor dc component. Also, phase-neutral voltage, U_{an} , is displayed. In Figs. 7 and 8, some waveforms with fault at 25% of the phase impedance are presented for different fault resistances. In these figures, the faulty phase voltage U_{cn} has a phase difference with respect to U_{gnd} of approximately 180° . In terms of amplitude, the higher the fault resistance value, the lower the amplitude of U_{gnd} .

By comparing Figs. 8 with 9, both wherein the ground fault resistance is set at $10 \text{ k}\Omega$, but in the first one the fault being performed at 25% of the phase impedance and in the second one at 75%, it can be noticed that the closer the fault to the neutral of the RL load, the lower the amplitude of U_{gnd} .

Once the fundamental harmonic is calculated with (10)–(12) for each phase voltage and the resistor ground voltage, the registered waveforms are compared to see which phase has a 180° phase difference with U_{gnd} . An example is plotted in

TABLE II
SIMULATION RESULTS FOR GROUND FAULTS ON PHASE “C”

Initial conditions		Voltage Phasors (First Harmonic)				Phase difference			Estimated location
AC Fault resistance, R_f	Real fault location, k	U_{an} [V]	U_{bn} [V]	U_{cn} [V]	U_{gnd} [V]	θ_{a-gnd} [°]	θ_{b-gnd} [°]	θ_{c-gnd} [°]	k (x100)
0	0	$242.91 \cdot e^{-j91.09^\circ}$	$242.45 \cdot e^{j148.84^\circ}$	$242.44 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$0.1960 \cdot e^{j152.44^\circ}$	116.47	-3.59	-123.47	-2.36
	25	$242.83 \cdot e^{-j91.06^\circ}$	$242.37 \cdot e^{j148.81^\circ}$	$242.60 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$60.480 \cdot e^{-j151.16^\circ}$	60.10	-60.03	-179.87	25.1
	50	$242.80 \cdot e^{-j91.05^\circ}$	$242.34 \cdot e^{j148.80^\circ}$	$242.65 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$120.90 \cdot e^{-j151.09^\circ}$	60.05	-60.10	-179.93	50.0
	75	$242.82 \cdot e^{-j91.06^\circ}$	$242.37 \cdot e^{j148.81^\circ}$	$242.60 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$181.54 \cdot e^{-j150.08^\circ}$	60.02	-60.11	-179.95	75.0
	100	$242.89 \cdot e^{-j91.09^\circ}$	$242.45 \cdot e^{j148.84^\circ}$	$242.43 \cdot e^{j28.96^\circ}$	$242.66 \cdot e^{-j150.07^\circ}$	59.98	-60.19	-179.96	100
2.3 kΩ	0	$242.91 \cdot e^{-j91.09^\circ}$	$242.45 \cdot e^{j148.84^\circ}$	$242.45 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$0.1317 \cdot e^{j152.58^\circ}$	116.32	-3.74	-123.61	-2.43
	25	$242.89 \cdot e^{-j91.08^\circ}$	$242.39 \cdot e^{j148.82^\circ}$	$242.55 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$40.662 \cdot e^{-j151.16^\circ}$	60.09	-60.02	-179.87	25.3
	50	$242.88 \cdot e^{-j91.07^\circ}$	$242.38 \cdot e^{j148.81^\circ}$	$242.59 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$81.274 \cdot e^{-j151.09^\circ}$	60.03	-60.09	-179.93	50.0
	75	$242.88 \cdot e^{-j91.08^\circ}$	$242.40 \cdot e^{j148.82^\circ}$	$242.55 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$121.98 \cdot e^{-j150.07^\circ}$	60.00	-60.10	-179.96	75.0
	100	$242.91 \cdot e^{-j91.09^\circ}$	$242.45 \cdot e^{j148.84^\circ}$	$242.44 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$162.86 \cdot e^{-j150.07^\circ}$	59.97	-60.09	-179.97	100
4.7 kΩ	0	$242.91 \cdot e^{-j91.09^\circ}$	$242.45 \cdot e^{j148.84^\circ}$	$242.47 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$0.0982 \cdot e^{j152.66^\circ}$	116.25	-3.81	-123.69	-2.47
	25	$242.87 \cdot e^{-j91.08^\circ}$	$242.41 \cdot e^{j149.83^\circ}$	$242.53 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$30.301 \cdot e^{-j150.16^\circ}$	60.08	-60.02	-179.87	25.5
	50	$242.86 \cdot e^{-j91.07^\circ}$	$242.39 \cdot e^{j149.82^\circ}$	$242.55 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$60.561 \cdot e^{-j150.09^\circ}$	60.02	-60.08	-179.93	50.1
	75	$242.87 \cdot e^{-j91.08^\circ}$	$242.41 \cdot e^{j149.83^\circ}$	$242.52 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$90.874 \cdot e^{-j150.07^\circ}$	60.00	-60.10	-179.96	75.0
	100	$242.90 \cdot e^{-j91.09^\circ}$	$242.45 \cdot e^{j148.84^\circ}$	$242.44 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$121.28 \cdot e^{-j150.07^\circ}$	59.97	-60.09	-179.97	100
10 kΩ	0	$242.91 \cdot e^{-j91.09^\circ}$	$242.45 \cdot e^{j148.84^\circ}$	$242.45 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$0.0628 \cdot e^{j152.75^\circ}$	116.16	-3.90	-123.78	-2.52
	25	$242.86 \cdot e^{-j91.08^\circ}$	$242.42 \cdot e^{j149.84^\circ}$	$242.50 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$19.390 \cdot e^{-j150.16^\circ}$	60.07	-60.01	-179.87	25.7
	50	$242.84 \cdot e^{-j91.08^\circ}$	$242.41 \cdot e^{j149.83^\circ}$	$242.51 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$38.751 \cdot e^{-j150.09^\circ}$	60.01	-60.08	-179.93	50.1
	75	$242.85 \cdot e^{-j91.08^\circ}$	$242.42 \cdot e^{j149.84^\circ}$	$242.50 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$58.134 \cdot e^{-j150.07^\circ}$	59.99	-60.09	-179.96	75.0
	100	$242.90 \cdot e^{-j91.09^\circ}$	$242.45 \cdot e^{j148.84^\circ}$	$242.44 \cdot e^{j28.97^\circ}$	$77.555 \cdot e^{-j150.06^\circ}$	59.97	-60.09	-179.97	100

Fig. 10. U_{an} , U_{bn} , U_{cn} , and U_{gnd} fundamental harmonic waveforms for an operation with a ground fault [$R_f = 4.7$ kΩ located at $k = 100\%$ of Z_C].

Fig. 11. Fundamental harmonic simulation U_{gnd} waveforms for ground fault operation with [$R_f = 0$ Ω and $k = 0\%$, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% of Z_C].

Fig. 10 for a 4.7 kΩ fault resistance, located at 100% of the RL load. The faulty phase is clearly phase “c,” as U_{cn} and U_{gnd} are out of phase by 180°.

A large number of simulations with different ac fault resistance values were done to verify the method and their results are displayed in Table II. The method is based on phase unbalance and the U_{gnd} variations when a ground fault occurs. In Figs. 11 and 12, U_{gnd} and U_{cn} variations can be seen, respectively, for direct ground faults ($R_f = 0$ Ω) and located at 0%, 25%, 50%,

75%, and 100%. These variations are higher in U_{gnd} than in U_{cn} due to the high value of R_{gnd} . However, these differences allow to compute k applying (9).

As it can be seen in Table II, the method is validated applying fundamental harmonic analysis.

Once the voltage phasors are calculated, no large phase fluctuations have been observed throughout the simulations when varying k or R_f . From Table II, it can be seen that the maximum angle variations are around $\pm 0.04^\circ$ between phase voltages and $\pm 0.11^\circ$ between U_{gnd} for different ground faults. In terms of voltage amplitudes, the oscillations in phase voltages are around ± 0.21 V for self-voltage variations (in U_{cn}) and ± 0.34 V between phases (U_{cn} and U_{an}). These variations make the second term of the product of (9) different from zero. At the same time, the changes in the amplitude value of U_{gnd} are more pronounced as they are directly proportional to I_{res} . It implies the variation of the first term of the product in (9). Then, high accuracy measurement devices should be used to correctly estimate the small differences between phase voltages.

In order to locate the fault, the different phase voltage phasors shall be compared in terms of phase, as shown in Table II. As noted before, a 180° phase difference between a phase voltage and U_{gnd} means that the fault is located on that phase. In case of a fault at 0% (or neutral-to-ground faults), the phase difference is around 120° for all phases.

Finally, the resulting fault location estimations for each case have been also displayed in Table II. The results demonstrate that the method presents a high accuracy level under simulation conditions. In terms of k , the estimation error is higher when the fault is closer to the center star.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Some experimental tests were carried out using a 140 kW power converter in order to verify the method.

Fig. 12. First harmonic simulation phase voltage waveforms for faults on phase “c” with arc resistance [$R_f = 0 \Omega$ and locations at 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% of Z_c].

TABLE III
EXPERIMENTAL SETUP COMPONENTS

Component	Parameter	Magnitude
Battery	U_{DC}	480 V
	U_{DC} per cell	12 V/cell
	Modules per String	40
	I_N	3.6 A
	Q	12 Ah
Inverter	Internal R	12 m Ω
	P	140 kW
	U_{DC} max.	900 V
	I_{out} max.	200 A
	f max.	25 kHz
	C	1638 μ F
	L_{filter}	3 mH
AC Impedance	R_{unit}	12.5 Ω

Fig. 13. 480 V_{dc} battery pack with the midpoint accessible.

The experimental setup consists of a battery pack of 40 cells in series with a 480 V_{dc} output, a 140 kW – 6 pulses-IGBTs power converter connected to the terminals of the battery pack, and a number of resistive loads connected in series to 3 mH inductive filters in the three-phase output of the converter. The ratings of the system can be seen in Table III and its topology corresponds to the topology displayed in Fig. 2.

Before doing experimental faulty tests, a 4.72 k Ω grounding resistor was connected between the midpoint of the batteries and ground. The batteries can be seen in Fig. 13. The batteries feed the 6 pulses-IGBT 140 kW power converter (see Fig. 14), which feed a three-phase ac star connected impedance, (see Fig. 15). The power converter works as a voltage source converter keeping the voltage constant at the ac terminals. The ac impedances are made up on each phase of four equal resistors of 12.5 Ω each, connected in series. These connections allow to perform ground faults at 0% (star center), 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% of the whole phase impedance.

In order to obtain a higher accuracy level throughout the tests, a precise impedance measurement has been done using frequency response analysis technique, FRA, which is commonly used in transformer or rotatory electrical machines diagnosis [35], [36]. The results for a frequency of 50 Hz were $51.21e^{j0.1^\circ}$, $50.88e^{j0.1^\circ}$, and $51.29e^{j0.1^\circ}$ for Z_a , Z_b , and Z_c , respectively.

Once the system was correctly characterized, the experimental tests were carried out.

First of all, a healthy condition test was performed to verify that the system worked correctly. The results for the phase voltages and grounding resistor voltage were collected and displayed in Figs. 16 and 17. In this last figure, it can be seen that U_{gnd} has a null value. High-frequency voltage fluctuations appear due to parasitic capacitances and phase-to-ground capacitances as R_{gnd} has high values. However, these high values of R_{gnd} allow high resistance fault detections, as the fault voltage is divided between it and R_f [16].

After having properly validated the system according to the results observed in the healthy tests, some ground faults have been carried out on the ac inverter side.

The faults were performed at 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% of the phase-impedance on phase “a.” Also, different ac fault resistance values, R_f , were tested (0 Ω , 2.3 k Ω , 4.7 k Ω , and 10 k Ω) to emulate different fault severities. Variations up from 200% of R_{gnd} will not note high differences in the study [16].

In Figs. 18–20, some faults are displayed. The first two figures correspond to a fault at the same point but with different R_f . Here, the U_{gnd} amplitude attenuation can be seen as R_f gets

Fig. 14. 140 kW power converter cupboard.

Fig. 15. Resistive load with a switching element to change the fault location.

Fig. 16. Phase to neutral voltages (U_{an} , U_{bn} , and U_{cn}) for healthy state operation.

larger. From Figs. 18 to 20, only the fault location changes from 25% to 75%, without changing R_f . This difference provokes an increase in the U_{gnd} amplitude. As R_{gnd} gets larger (in order to limit the fault current), the phase voltages (U_{an} , U_{bn} , or U_{cn}) do not experience appreciable changes.

Fig. 17. Phase “a” to neutral voltage, U_{an} , and grounding resistor voltage, U_{gnd} , under healthy operation condition.

Fig. 18. U_{an} and U_{gnd} voltage waveforms for an operation with a ground fault with arc resistance $R_f = 2.3 \text{ k}\Omega$ located at 25% of the phase impedance.

Fig. 19. U_{an} and U_{gnd} voltage waveforms for an operation with a ground fault with arc resistance $R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$ located at 25% of the phase impedance.

Furthermore, another important fact is that the faulty phase voltage has a 180° phase difference with U_{gnd} (counter-phase). In Fig. 21, some vectorial diagrams are plotted to draw this idea. The out-of-phase property allows an easy determination of the faulty phase.

Once all the faults were accomplished, signal processing was performed through (10)–(12). Then, (9) was applied in order to compute the fault location factor k . The results obtained are collected in Table IV.

In this table, it can be seen that for low fault resistances the location system works with higher accuracy. In contrast, for large values of R_f (4.7 k Ω or 10 k Ω), the results are less accurate. This fact is due to the low fault current that makes the resolution obtained in R_{gnd} low.

In terms of absolute errors in the fault location estimation, it can be seen that errors up to 3.94% are obtained for direct ground faults ($R_f = 0 \text{ }\Omega$). For higher values of R_f , the errors increase up

Fig. 20. U_{an} and U_{gnd} voltage waveforms for an operation with a ground fault with arc resistance, $R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$ located in the 75% of the phase impedance.

Fig. 21. Phasor diagrams for U_{an} , U_{bn} , U_{cn} , and U_{gnd} for ground faults at 0%. (a) 25%. (b) 50%. (c) 75%. (d) of Z_a .

TABLE IV
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Initial conditions		Phase difference	Estimated location
AC Fault resistance, R_f	Real fault location, k	θ_{a-gnd} [°]	k (x100)
0	0	24.95	495.2
	25	178.47	26.84
	50	-178.61	53.94
	75	-179.33	72.74
	100	-179.96	102.9
2.3 kΩ	0	-103.43	-2483
	25	-177.69	31.27
	50	-178.38	56.65
	75	-179.88	79.01
	100	179.54	104.8
4.7 kΩ	0	-97.21	-2886
	25	-178.49	37.33
	50	-178.38	56.15
	75	179.51	72.92
	100	-179.28	98.60
10 kΩ	0	-144.59	-3407
	25	-177.07	26.57
	50	-179.98	44.39
	75	179.37	90.80
	100	-179.86	111.0

Fig. 22. Ground fault location estimation error attending to the phase impedance estimation deviation.

to 15.80% ($R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$). The errors obtained with this method are similar to other inventions referred to the current state of the art. In [22] the average error is 2.20% for $R_f = 300 \Omega$ but not higher arc resistances were tested and more variables and parameters are used. In [27], errors of 16.41% for $R_f = 200 \Omega$ are achieved. And for dc location methods 9.75% for $R_f = 1.317 \Omega$ in [29] and 5.98% for $R_f = 2 \Omega$ in [32] are achieved. Most of these methods achieve less error than the method proposed in this article. However, for high R_f , all of them probably would reach less accurate results than the proposed in this article. The higher the fault resistance sensitivity is, the earliest the fault can be located. In this case, the proposed method locates faults with R_f around 30–50 times higher than other methods.

One problem that the method could present is related to the impedance estimation, which affects directly in the fault location, as pointed in (9). Fig. 22 depicts a sensitivity analysis of the method, where maximum errors achieved in the location estimation are plotted attending to the error in the impedance estimation for different values of $R_f = 0 \Omega$. It can be seen that Z errors affect considerably to low R_f ground faults cases. Although high R_f faults have bigger fault location errors, deviations in Z are not as noticeable as for low R_f faults.

Another problem to consider is the neutral-to-ground fault proximity. In this way, the nearer the fault to the neutral, the less accurate the method. This is because the fault current decreases with its proximity to the neutral. Furthermore, the resolution in R_{gnd} decreases. As it can be seen in Table IV, the values obtained for 0% are not suitable. However, this type of fault near to the star center can be detected by the angle comparison between phases and U_{gnd} , where none of them has 180° of difference with U_{gnd} , but U_{gnd} waveform still having other frequency components different from 0 V, e.g., the commutation frequency of the inverter.

Finally, it must be remarked that the method presents an acceptable accuracy for the rest of fault locations, especially for low R_f , and it can be implemented as a plugging to already developed systems [16].

VI. CONCLUSION

Variable speed drives are nowadays widely used in power systems. However, the layout of the variable speed drives requires the presence of both dc and ac sides in order to adapt the power

to different operating conditions. This makes the protection of the whole system a difficult task. In order to locate the controlled ac drive side ground faults, a new location method is presented in this article.

The proposed method is based on a grounding resistor connected between the midpoint of the dc bus and ground. The voltage at the terminals of this resistor as well as the phase-neutral ac voltages on the controlled ac side of the drive are analyzed. If a ground fault takes place on this side, a voltage waveform shows up in the grounding resistor.

The faulty phase can be identified by comparing the phase of the grounding resistor voltage phasor to the phase-neutral voltage phasors. The phase-neutral voltage phasor of the faulty phase is 180° out-of-phase (counter-phase) to the grounding resistor voltage phasor. The location of the ground fault is also computed. Phase impedances shall be known, and fundamental harmonic analysis of the voltage waveforms shall be performed. The method requires the correct operation of the converter switching transistor. Therefore, the converter should withstand the overvoltages produced during the ground faults, especially in the case of high resistance grounding.

To verify the method, numerous simulations were carried out and experimental tests using a 140 kW – 6 pulses IGBTs power converter were performed, achieving satisfactory results. Some points should be remarked. First, the existence of a ground fault provokes an unbalance that is used to locate the fault; the higher the fault resistance, the smaller the unbalance provoked. Second, it must be taken into consideration that the sensitivity decreases in case of high ground fault resistances located close to the neutral of the load. This last location could be estimated by angle comparison between U_{gnd} and the phase-neutral voltages, where none of them has 180° difference. Also, further works should be focused on other frequencies examination in order to solve the problem.

However, the accuracy of the method stays competitive against similar ground fault location methods and it is remarkably sensible to higher fault resistance faults than other ground fault location methods, which allow to make early diagnosis of this type of faults.

Finally, it must be highlighted that the ground fault resistance is not an incognita in the location process. The method can be used as an add-on for other detection methods on dc or ac sides of variable speed drives when the fault is in the controlled ac drive side.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. M. Guerrero, G. Navarro, and C. A. Platano, "AC ground fault location method for frequency converters based on AC phases and grounding resistor voltage measurements," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Environ. Elect. Eng.; IEEE Ind. Commercial Power Syst. Europe*, Jun. 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [2] R. Barrera-Cardenas and M. Molinas, "Comparative study of wind turbine power converters based on medium-frequency AC-link for offshore DC-grids," *IEEE J. Emerg. Sel. Topics Power Electron.*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 525–541, Jun. 2015.
- [3] R. Basak, G. Bhuvaneswari, and R. R. Pillai, "Low-voltage ride-through of a synchronous generator-based variable speed grid-interfaced wind energy conversion system," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 752–762, Jan./Feb. 2020.
- [4] M. D. Bhandari and J. K. Chavda, "Ultra-capacitor based three level bi-directional isolated DC–DC converter for the regenerative braking energy recovery system," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Inf., Commun., Instrum. Control*, 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [5] N. Weise, "DQ current control of a bidirectional, isolated, single-stage AC–DC converter for vehicle-to-grid applications," in *Proc. IEEE Power Energy Soc. Gen. Meeting*, 2013, pp. 1–5.
- [6] T. Horiguchi *et al.*, "A high-speed protection circuit for IGBTs subjected to hard-switching faults," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 51, no. 2, pp. 1774–1781, Mar./Apr. 2015.
- [7] X. Xie, W. Liu, H. Liu, Y. Du, and Y. Li, "A system-wide protection against unstable SSCI in series-compensated wind power systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 3095–3104, Dec. 2018.
- [8] L. Qi, M. Carminati, and M. Riva, "Fault interruption and protection coordination in converter interfaced distribution systems," in *Proc. IEEE Power Energy Soc. Gen. Meeting*, 2018, pp. 1–5.
- [9] J. D. Gardell *et al.*, "Adjustable-speed drive motor protection applications and issues," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 1364–1372, Mar./Apr. 2014.
- [10] S. Roy, M. K. Alam, F. Khan, J. Johnson, and J. Flicker, "An irradiance-independent, robust ground-fault detection scheme for PV arrays based on spread spectrum time-domain reflectometry (SSTDTR)," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 33, no. 8, pp. 7046–7057, Aug. 2018.
- [11] T. Gush *et al.*, "Fault detection and location in a microgrid using mathematical morphology and recursive least square methods," *Int. J. Elect. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 102, pp. 324–331, 2018.
- [12] S. Zhang, S. Lin, Z. He, and W. Lee, "Ground fault location in radial distribution networks involving distributed voltage measurement," *IET Gener., Transmiss., Distrib.*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 987–996, Feb. 2018.
- [13] J. Hu, L. Wei, J. McGuire, and Z. Liu, "Faulted phase location identification for adjustable speed drives in high-resistance grounding system," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 54, no. 5, pp. 4457–4463, Sep./Oct. 2018.
- [14] R. P. Bataglioli, R. M. Monaro, and D. V. Coury, "Differential protection for stator ground faults in a full-converter wind turbine generator," *Electric Power Syst. Res.*, vol. 169, pp. 195–205, 2019.
- [15] F. R. Blázquez, C. A. Platano, E. Rebollo, and F. Blázquez, "Novel rotor ground-fault detection algorithm for synchronous machines with static excitation based on third-harmonic voltage-phasor comparison," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 2548–2558, Apr. 2016.
- [16] J. M. Guerrero, G. Navarro, C. A. Platano, P. Tian, and F. Blázquez, "A novel ground fault detection method for electric vehicle powertrains based on a grounding resistor voltage analysis," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 56, no. 5, pp. 4934–4944, Sep./Oct. 2020.
- [17] S. A. Gopalan, V. Sreeram, and H. H. C. Iu, "A review of coordination strategies and protection schemes for microgrids," *Renewable Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 32, pp. 222–228, 2014.
- [18] M. M. Eissa, "Ground distance relay compensation based on fault resistance calculation," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 1830–1835, Oct. 2006.
- [19] V. H. Makwana and B. R. Bhalja, "A new digital distance relaying scheme for compensation of high-resistance faults on transmission line," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 2133–2140, Oct. 2012.
- [20] Q. Lin, G. Luo, and J. He, "Travelling-wave-based method for fault location in multi-terminal DC networks," *J. Eng.*, vol. 2017, no. 13, pp. 2314–2318, 2017.
- [21] H. Liang, Y. Liu, G. Sheng, and X. Jiang, "Reproduction methodology for single phase-to-ground faults in overhead transmission lines," *IEEE Access*, vol. 5, pp. 17403–17413, 2017.
- [22] J. Ma, C. Liu, P. Cheng, and A. G. Phadke, "A novel AC line distance protection scheme for AC/DC hybrid system based on fault component energy equation," *Int. J. Elect. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 134, 2022, Art. no. 107393.
- [23] J. Pons-Llinares, J. A. Antonino-Daviu, M. Riera-Guasp, S. Bin Lee, T. Kang, and C. Yang, "Advanced induction motor rotor fault diagnosis via continuous and discrete time–frequency tools," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 1791–1802, Mar. 2015.
- [24] P. Nussbaumer, M. A. Vogelsberger, and T. M. Wolbank, "Induction machine insulation health state monitoring based on online switching transient exploitation," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 1835–1845, Mar. 2015.
- [25] G. Capolino, J. A. Antonino-Daviu, and M. Riera-Guasp, "Modern diagnostics techniques for electrical machines, power electronics, and drives," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 1738–1745, Mar. 2015.
- [26] C. A. Platano, M. Redondo, M. Pardo, and E. Rebollo, "Novel adaptive 100% stator ground fault protection based on the third harmonic measurement," in *Proc. XXII Int. Conf. Elect. Mach.*, 2016, pp. 2300–2305.

- [27] N. Safari-Shad, R. Franklin, A. Negahdari, and H. A. Toliyat, "Adaptive 100% injection-based generator stator ground fault protection with real-time fault location capability," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 2364–2372, Oct. 2018.
- [28] C. Zhang, J. Huang, G. Song, and X. Dong, "Non-unit ultra-high-speed line protection for multi-terminal hybrid LCC/MMC HVDC system and its application research," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 2825–2838, Sep. 2020.
- [29] J. Park, J. Candelaria, L. Ma, and K. Dunn, "DC ring-bus microgrid fault protection and identification of fault location," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 2574–2584, Oct. 2013.
- [30] Y. M. Yeap, N. Geddada, and A. Ukil, "Capacitive discharge based transient analysis with fault detection methodology in DC system," *Int. J. Elect. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 97, pp. 127–137, 2018.
- [31] T. Gruhn, J. Glenney, and M. Savostianik, "Type B ground-fault protection on adjustable frequency drives," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 54, no. 1, pp. 934–939, Jan./Feb. 2018.
- [32] S. Dhar, R. K. Patnaik, and P. K. Dash, "Fault detection and location of photovoltaic based DC microgrid using differential protection strategy," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4303–4312, Sep. 2018.
- [33] J. M. Guerrero and C. A. Platero, "Sistema y método de localización de faltas a tierra en instalaciones de corriente alterna," U.S. Patent ES 2758531 B2, Feb. 2021.
- [34] V. D. Andrade and E. Sorrentino, "Typical expected values of the fault resistance in power systems," in *Proc. IEEE/PES Transmiss. Distrib. Conf. Expo.: Latin America*, 2010, pp. 602–609.
- [35] E. Kornatowski and S. Banaszak, "Frequency response quality index for assessing the mechanical condition of transformer windings," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 115, Dec. 2019.
- [36] A. Mugarra, C. A. Platero, J. A. Martínez, and U. Albizuri-Txurruka, "Validity of frequency response analysis (FRA) for diagnosing large salient poles of synchronous machines," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 226–234, Jan./Feb. 2020.